

Uniting Under the Eclipse: A Mega-Collaboration to Activate Science Learning Across the Penumbra and Beyond

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports the extensive collaboration and innovative outreach efforts of NASA's Science Activation (SciAct) program surrounding the 2023-24 solar eclipses. SciAct, which leverages a collective impact model, brought together diverse teams to create a synergistic approach to public science education and engagement for the eclipses. Building on lessons from the 2017 eclipse, teams co-developed a range of multi-sensory and inclusive resources designed to reach diverse audiences across the continent. Materials included tactile and bilingual resources, citizen science tools, and hands-on activities distributed through various networks across the country. In addition to real-time eclipse engagement, SciAct emphasized data collection, with participatory science initiatives encouraging the public to contribute valuable environmental and audio data, and more importantly, to participate in analyzing and contributing to scientific results. The paper discusses how these collaborative efforts not only enhanced public understanding of solar science but also established long-term opportunities for sustaining engagement in science education. Through continuous collaboration, resource sharing, and adaptability, SciAct has demonstrated how large-scale efforts to activate science learning can maximize impact, reach diverse audiences, and create lasting educational experiences well beyond the eclipse events.

1. Introducing NASA's Science Activation Program

NASA's Science Activation (SciAct) program re-envisioned NASA's approach to science education and outreach. Initially launched in January 2016, SciAct leverages the unique assets of NASA's Science Mission Directorate (experts, content, and data) to foster learners' active participation in the advancement of human knowledge. The SciAct program accomplishes this by identifying and centering the needs of learner communities and working collaboratively to meet them where they are—across the nation and globally.

SciAct pursues this vision through periodic open solicitations. SciAct teams are selected for up to a 5-year period to allow for critical relationship-building and collaboration necessary to maximize impact toward program objectives. The SciAct program includes two types of teams: competitively-selected teams and foundational teams within NASA, called *infrastructure* teams, that provide critical expertise and assets needed to support SciAct outputs. The first solicitation in 2015 funded 27 competitively-selected teams. A recompetition in 2020-21 was informed by a formal assessment by the National Academies ([NASEM, 2020](#)). SciAct continued with approximately 70% of the original teams, while also substantially revising or adding 20 other teams to the program portfolio.

While broadening participation has always been a goal for SciAct, the 2020-21 solicitation in particular sought proposals “to broaden participation of under-represented and under-served learners in order to maximize participation in advancement of knowledge”. Projects selected from the second solicitation included several

teams that focused on serving the needs of very specific [audience segments](#) (i.e., neurodiverse learners, learners who are blind or have low vision, rural communities, etc.).

2. A Collaborative Approach to Engagement

The SciAct program is a collaborative network that has adopted key elements and approaches of the Collective Impact Model ([Kania & Kramer, 2011](#)). This model provides a set of guiding principles for portfolio activities and tools that foster, support, and reinforce collaboration in multiple ways (see [Figure 1](#)).

Figure 1

The Collective Impact model (Santo, 2019) with identification of activities and resources within SciAct that support each of the five elements in peripheral boxes.

A small group at NASA serves as the “backbone organization” that supports, leads, and coordinates collaboration across the collaborative, nationwide network of 48 SciAct teams. The program achieves its impressive nationwide and international reach in two primary ways:

- Teams enter into **cross-collaborations** to leverage each other’s assets and expertise. This prevents duplication of effort and promotes efficiency in accomplishing shared goals.
- Teams also engage in **strategic partnerships** with community- and audience-based organizations to support institutional, state, and local efforts that help them best achieve their objectives and meet the needs of diverse learners. Since the SciAct program began in 2016, the number of partnerships has more than doubled, with teams reporting 590 active external partners in 2023 and over 1,100 in 2024.

Key aspects of this collaborative approach that led to increased impact during the eclipse events included monthly and annual meetings that built strong relationships over time, collaboration support tools to facilitate internal communication, the ongoing requirement for cross-collaboration to reduce duplication and overlap of resources and accustomed projects to coordinate with and rely on each other, and a shared vision statement, top- and mid-level objectives.

A critical element was a SciAct Eclipse *Community of Practice*—a pop-up affinity group that formed months before the annular eclipse. This Eclipse Group met monthly and provided a forum for interested teams to share and refine their plans with each other and coordinate with the larger NASA eclipse collective ([Korreck et al., 2025](#)). This not only allowed SciAct teams to maximize their collective impact, but it also extended their impact beyond the SciAct community and into other parts of NASA.

3. Solar Eclipses and SciAct: Expanding and Scaling Activation

The cluster of recent solar eclipses across North America offered a unique opportunity for SciAct to work together at scale to reach diverse learners across the entire nation—and beyond. Since its inception in 2016, SciAct has had three key eclipse opportunities: first with the 2017 Eclipse Across America, then the [2023 Annular Solar Eclipse](#), and most recently the [2024 Total Solar Eclipse](#). Some SciAct teams also worked in South America in 2019/20.

The initial solicitation and selection of 27 SciAct teams in 2016 included consideration for teams that would address the August 2017 Solar Eclipse Across America. Four teams were selected to specifically focus on the eclipse ([Citizen CATE](#), Heliophysics Education Consortium (now [NASA HEAT](#)), [Navigating the Path of Totality](#), and [Smoky Mountains STEM Collaborative](#)), with a few other teams also engaged in activities related to the eclipse (i.e., [NASA@My Library](#) supported distribution of eclipse glasses through local libraries, [NASA Earth Science Education Collaborative](#) (NESEC) added a tool to the [GLOBE Observer](#) app to enable volunteers to report eclipse effects on air temperature and cloud cover, [Infiniscope](#) created an interactive eclipse lesson that leveraged the [NASA Eyes](#) app). A SciAct-funded project from the [University of Michigan](#) deployed a national survey to understand the impact of the 2017 eclipse on public science literacy. The final report on public viewing, [Americans and the 2017 Eclipse](#) ([Miller, 2018](#)), showed that 88% of US adults engaged with the 2017 eclipse either in person or digitally (minors were not included in the survey). This finding confirmed the importance of eclipses as a learning opportunity, when the attention of much of the population is drawn to such a notable event.

From the 2020-21 solicitation, four new teams were intentionally selected to support engagement efforts around the 2023 and 2024 eclipses ([Eclipse Ambassadors](#), [Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science Project](#), [Nationwide Eclipse Ballooning Project](#), [Science through Shadows](#)). With three of the prior four teams continuing (Citizen CATE continued outside SciAct), this meant seven teams were dedicated to eclipse education and engagement efforts in the SciAct portfolio of 48 teams. With the experience of the 2017 Solar

Eclipse Across America to guide them, the more established SciAct community rallied around the 2023-24 eclipses as an opportunity to activate learning based on established relationships that had strengthened and deepened since the SciAct program began. The eclipse-focused teams had 2-3 years leading up to the October 2023 Annular Eclipse to hone tools and approaches to serve their audiences; and, crucially, share them across the SciAct collective so they could be applied more widely.

With many opportunities for collaboration and the broad availability of Eclipse resources from various teams, the barriers to Eclipse engagement were lowered for other teams in the SciAct network. This drove participation in 2023 and 2024 eclipse engagement well beyond the seven core eclipse-focused teams to ultimately span many SciAct teams—fully three-quarters of 48 active SciAct teams were substantially involved in these two celestial events.

As an additional promotional boost, as SciAct eclipse preparations were ramping up, NASA's Heliophysics Division declared a [Helio Big Year](#) (HBY; borrowing the Big Year concept from the birder community), starting with the annular eclipse in Oct. 2023 and running through Parker Solar Probe's closest approach to the Sun in Dec. 2024, as a way to organize around a variety of heliophysics topics and opportunities. SciAct eclipse efforts were well-positioned to also participate under this broader NASA engagement umbrella, further motivating teams to prepare and cross-promote resources. This established pathways for engagement across the teams and projects that could be strengthened and deepened before the total eclipse in April of 2024.

4. Mega-Collaboration leads to Mega Results

The 2024 eclipse engagement efforts through NASA's SciAct program achieved remarkable reach, engaging learners across numerous platforms and events. SciAct teams reported a total of more than **66 million learner interactions** connected to the 2024 eclipse. Figure 2 shows a summary of the efforts and offerings from the SciAct program and its tremendous capacity to scale, reaching millions of learners of all ages across the Nation through tens of thousands of programs and events leveraging hundreds of resources developed for the eclipse by SciAct teams.

NASA Science Activation Solar Eclipse Engagement By the Numbers

Figure 2
NASA Science Activation Summary of Offerings and Reach for 2024 Solar Eclipse Engagement Efforts.

For context, [Table 1](#) shows the program-wide annual total learner interactions¹ for SciAct since 2019, when this data collection began. Reach during the 2024 eclipse stands second only to calendar year 2023.

Table 1

SciAct Full Year Activities					Eclipse Only
2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024 Eclipse
15 M	23 M	21 M	52 M	76 M	66 M

Table 1. Historical and Eclipse reach of the SciAct community: total annual learner interactions across all SciAct projects compared with the reach during the 2024 Eclipse.

Reach extended across all 50 states, all US territories (Pacific territories were reached in relation to an earlier eclipse in that region), and even beyond U.S. borders, showcasing the nationwide interest in eclipse science and the extensive reach of SciAct. [Figure 3](#) shows all the locations where SciAct teams reported reaching learners. While efforts were concentrated along and near the path of totality², teams also targeted major population centers around the country, in addition to more remote and rural areas.

Figure 3

Locations where SciAct teams reported reaching learners for the 2024 total solar eclipse.

The Eclipse Ambassadors team, in particular, focused on reaching communities off the path of totality. [Figure 4](#) shows the location of eclipse ambassador events on a map highlighting counties that have above-average representation of Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander, American Indian or Alaska Native, Multiracial, Asian, Black or African American, and/or Hispanic or Latino populations, represented by increasingly intense shades of green. More than 80% (948 of 1,174) Eclipse Ambassador events occurred in counties with above-average representation of such populations, which are underrepresented in science, technology, engineering, or mathematics (STEM).

Figure 4

Location of eclipse ambassador events on a map showing counties with higher representation of underrepresented populations in shades of green. Darker green represents counties with higher proportions of more than one such population.

5. Understanding the Mechanisms of SciAct Collaboration

SciAct maintains a robust data infrastructure that allows for transparency across key dimensions of the collective impact model. Data calls are issued regularly to understand collective impact; a systems analysis capability maximizes insights from those data. The large scope and volume of engagement activities and reach around the 2024 solar eclipse provided a unique opportunity to examine SciAct operating at scale. A brief survey was developed (Appendix A [Table 3](#)) that asked SciAct teams to report on the nature of their collaborations and the resources they utilized in their solar eclipse engagement activities. The survey was distributed three days after the 2024 eclipse, while eclipse activities were fresh and at the height of reflection and SciAct conversation about activities and outcomes. Specific questions of interest were:

1. How did SciAct teams utilize NASA assets from Infrastructure teams in their solar eclipse activities?
2. How did SciAct teams collaborate with each other around the solar eclipse?
3. Could we identify critical clusters of activity and collaboration to develop case studies/success stories?

In the month that followed the eclipse, a total of 37 teams (77% of the portfolio) responded to the survey. Draft data visualizations were created and shared with the teams for review and validation of the analysis and results. A few additions and adjustments were made, leading to the final results shared in the following sections.

SciAct teams collaborate in various ways, including knowledge sharing, resource and product sharing, and working together to deliver programs and services. Survey data shows the extent to which teams reported engaging in each of these three types of collaborations, as well as in various combinations (see [Figure 5](#)). Overall, there were 154 unique instances of collaboration. This analysis also allowed us to examine how teams combined different kinds of collaboration to deepen their relationships. We were able to see which teams shared narrowly focused collaborations, or where a pair of teams included multiple kinds of collaboration that could serve to deepen network ties and build pathways of engagement for learners moving forward. The Venn diagram in [Figure 5](#) shows the frequency and distribution of each of the various possible combinations of collaboration types reported among teams. Survey data shows that teams reported all possible combinations of collaboration activities, with product and resource sharing being the most frequent type of collaboration (N=43), followed by team collaborations including all three types of collaborations examined (N=40).

Figure 5

Number of collaborations that SciAct teams reported surrounding eclipse activities by type of collaboration. Note that most teams collaborated with more than one other team.

5.1. Resource Sharing Across the Network

Central to the success of the SciAct model is how well teams can leverage NASA’s unique assets, and how efficiently and effectively they can collaborate to share knowledge and resources among the network. Resources can include video, digital tools, presentations, handouts, and other materials useful for learner

engagement. A Zenodo community (https://zenodo.org/communities/sciact_eclipse) has been developed to archive these SciAct eclipse resources for the long term, in anticipation of the next US eclipse in 2044.

Resource sharing was measured as *one-directional* USAGE that flowed from a resource **provider** to a team **consumer**. Results were visualized using a Sankey diagram, a data visualization technique that shows flow/movement/change over time ([Otto et al., 2022](#)). This interactive visualization ([link here](#)) allows viewers to isolate and highlight individual teams and view the teams that they either provided to or utilized resources from during eclipse activities (see [Figure 6](#)). These data visualization tools helped SciAct better understand the flow of assets and collaborations surrounding the eclipse and provide evidence that there was a substantial leveraging of assets across the network. Note that many teams appear on both sides of the diagram, as both producers of resources and users of each other's resources. See Appendix B ([Table 4](#)) for the Team names and their abbreviations used in [Figure 6](#), [Figure 7](#), and [Figure 8](#).

Figure 6

The flow of products/resources from 29 provider teams to 31 consumer teams shows a substantial leveraging of assets across and among teams.

[Link to interactive here.](#)

NASA Infrastructure teams were also a critical source of eclipse assets, data, and resources. Thirty teams reported using NASA Infrastructure assets in their eclipse efforts, and the resulting data ([link to interactive here](#)) shows a pattern (see [Figure 7](#)) of robust asset sharing that is similar in frequency to team-to-team sharing.

Figure 7
 The directional flow of products/resources from 22 NASA Infrastructure sources to 29 competitively-funded teams shows a substantial leveraging of NASA assets across and among teams. [Link to interactive here.](#)

The pairing of data about the use of NASA Infrastructure assets with resource sharing among teams provides further insights into the flow of resources across the network. This enables the tracking of resources from infrastructure teams to those that adapted or produced resources, and ultimately to the teams that consumed

Figure 9

Arc diagram showing the *programmatic collaborations* between SciAct teams surrounding the 2024 eclipse. Competed teams are represented in blue text and infrastructure teams are in orange text. Connections between funded teams are shown with blue arcs, while connections between infrastructure teams and funded teams are represented by orange arcs.

[Link to interactive here.](#)

Figure 10

Isolating and visualizing the many program collaborations for the Eclipse Ambassadors team shows a cluster of eclipse programmatic activity within the SciAct network. [Link to interactive here.](#)

Stories that feature program development and collaboration are detailed in Section 7.

5.3 Interdisciplinary Knowledge Sharing

Sharing knowledge and expertise is a fundamental mechanism for more effectively reaching and engaging learners across the network ([NASEM, 2022](#)). While one team has expertise to support English language learners, another team knows how to adapt visuals and materials for blind and low vision learners. Teams also

engaged in knowledge and information sharing to support their instructional design efforts and to integrate subject matter experts into their eclipse activities. **Knowledge sharing** was measured as a connection between teams. Results were visualized using an [interactive arc diagram](#) (see [Figure 11](#)) that allows viewers to isolate and highlight individual teams to see the number of knowledge-sharing collaborations that they engaged in during eclipse activities, as well as the teams that they partnered with for these programs—using the interactive arc diagram to visualize data allowed SciAct to identify important sources of knowledge in the SciAct collaborative, and see how that knowledge propagated through the community to benefit more learners (see [Figure 12](#)).

Figure 11

Arc diagram showing **Knowledge Sharing** between SciAct teams surrounding the 2024 eclipse. Funded teams are represented in blue text and infrastructure teams are in orange text. Connections between funded teams are shown with blue arcs, while connections between infrastructure teams and funded teams are represented by orange arcs. [Link to interactive here.](#)

Figure 12

Isolating and visualizing the knowledge sharing collaborations of the Eclipse Ambassadors team shows how extensively knowledge was mobilized across the SciAct network.

[Link to interactive here.](#)

Stories featuring knowledge sharing collaborations are detailed in Section 8.

6. Examples of Resource Sharing

6.1. Co-Developing Resources, Materials, and Experiences

In order to share assets, one must first create those assets. Here we share a few examples of eclipse assets that were created for specific audiences or outlets.

Expert-Led Resource Development

[NASA HEAT](#), based in the Heliophysics Division at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, meticulously designed a range of engagement activities to enhance public understanding and enjoyment of the 2023 annular and 2024 total solar eclipses. These activities were crafted based on lessons learned in 2017 and with a focus on accessibility, inclusivity, and hands-on learning, ensuring that participants of all ages and backgrounds could connect with the science behind these celestial events. The activities included interactive demonstrations, educational games, and hands-on projects such as building pinhole projectors and solar viewers ([Sasser et al., 2024](#)). Each activity was carefully aligned with NASA's broader educational goals, emphasizing key concepts in heliophysics, safe viewing practices, and the cultural significance of eclipses. To ensure these activities could be effectively implemented across diverse communities, HEAT provided comprehensive resources that included step-by-step guides, printable materials, and visual aids. As indicated in the inset (which is linked to the interactive visualization), these resources were picked up and used across 25 SciAct teams.

To maximize the reach and impact of these engagement activities, HEAT offered extensive training for NASA staff, volunteers, and anyone interested in leading eclipse-related events. This training was delivered through multiple platforms, including in-person workshops, live webinars, and self-paced online modules available on NASA's internal platform for NASA employees. The training sessions covered essential topics such as the science of eclipses, safety protocols, effective communication strategies, NASA's citizen science projects related to the eclipse, and the use of NASA's educational resources.

Participants were equipped not only with the knowledge needed to facilitate activities but also with the skills to engage diverse audiences and address common questions. Additionally, HEAT provided access to a curated library of short demonstration videos and recorded webinars, ensuring that even those who could not attend live training sessions could still benefit from these resources. In particular, NASA HEAT made five popular hands-on [activities available](#) to NASA SunSpots - public engagement sites with a NASA presence along the path of totality - along with [training sessions](#) and short demonstration videos and recorded webinars, providing additional guidance and best practices for engaging audiences during the eclipse events. By empowering a broad network of trained facilitators, the HEAT team ensured that NASA's eclipse engagement activities could be delivered effectively and consistently across the nation, fostering widespread participation and enthusiasm for these extraordinary events.

More than 300 NASA employees and contractors who were involved in leading or participating in these activities, or who would interact with the media, successfully completed the multimedia-packed, interactive modules available on the internal NASA platform. Upon completing the course, participants could download editable training materials for further use with their own audiences. Additionally, through a partnership with

NASA, a similar version of the training was made available on the Oregon State University website, where it was downloaded 889 times.

NASA HEAT also developed and curated a comprehensive set of eclipse-related communications resources, including banners, posters, folders, fact sheets, safety flyers, and maps, all made available for public download. To ensure accessibility for diverse audiences, many of these materials were translated into multiple languages, including Arabic, Chinese, Korean, Spanish, Vietnamese, and Tagalog. These languages were chosen based on Census data as the most common additional languages spoken in the eclipse path. Select products were also printed for distribution at various NASA SunSpots where they were used to engage and educate the public. In preparation for the 2023 annular and 2024 total solar eclipses, NASA HEAT also collaborated with Neptune Studios to produce [eight eclipse-related videos](#) as part of the popular MinuteEarth and MinutePhysics series. These short, engaging, and illustrated videos cover a wide range of topics, including the science of eclipses, their history and cultural significance, the orbital mechanics behind them, unusual animal behaviors observed during eclipses, and eclipses occurring on other planets in our solar system. By April 8, 2024, these videos had garnered more than 4 million views, highlighting their broad appeal and educational impact. Additionally, MinuteEarth created a virtual lab called [Eclipse Explorer](#), providing an interactive platform for learners of all ages to explore solar eclipses as they occur on different planets across the solar system, further enhancing the educational experience surrounding these celestial events.

The [NESEC](#) team also produced a suite of science-based resources to provide connections between Earth and eclipse science. Its [GLOBE Observer](#) app engages volunteers of all ages in collecting environmental observations. The GLOBE Eclipse tool is activated during an eclipse to record temperature and cloud conditions. It focuses on the concept that the Sun drives many processes in the atmosphere and asks how an eclipse might impact those processes. To help facilitators communicate this science, NESEC produced a one-pager that could be printed as a poster or handout, a science video, and editable presentation slides. To support partner facilitators in leading GLOBE Eclipse data collection, NESEC produced a how-to video, a foldable pamphlet detailing data collection, paper data sheets, and a solar eclipse journal page. As shown in the inset, these resources were used by 17 SciAct teams, as well as

numerous external partners.

The team produced a variety of resources to support partners, including videos, handouts, activities, training presentations, display material, and recommendations for using resources in events and educational settings, all available in an [Eclipse toolkit for informal educators](#). This included seven videos in English and Spanish about Earth and eclipses. The first video focused on how to use the GLOBE Observer app to record changes in temperature and clouds during the eclipse, while the second provided information about how eclipses impact

atmospheric processes that NASA broadly studies. These were produced to enable partners to train audiences. NESEC also produced a series of seven short social media videos featuring NASA subject matter experts, which were distributed through NASA and GLOBE social media channels. To ensure access to all, the resources meet the highest accessibility standards. All resources were produced in both English and Spanish, and many were also translated into French to support audiences in Canada.

NESEC also provided hands-on activities, graphic assets, and tabletop display materials to support eclipse events. The NESEC team sent thermometers and activity supplies to interested NASA SunSpots and provided training to event planners. These materials were integrated into at least six large-scale events. Additionally, NESEC provided a media kit including talking points, b-roll, and images to support the promotion of NASA events and science.

NESEC encouraged partners to collect data with audiences and to create a GLOBE Team for their group. A GLOBE Team groups volunteer data within the GLOBE website (<https://www.globe.gov>) so that all members of the group can see data collected by their team. It also enabled NESEC to assess the impact of partnerships on data collection. Nearly 60 percent of air temperature data and 77 percent of cloud data collected during the eclipses came from partner teams. Initial analysis looked at the impact of the eclipse on cirrus clouds and contrails ([Autore et al., 2025](#)).

Data-Rich Resource Development

Building on the success of the widely popular 2017 "Eclipse Across America" map, NASA HEAT partnered with NASA's [Scientific Visualization Studio](#) (SVS) to create an [updated map](#) for the 2024 total solar eclipse ([Figure 13](#)). Eclipse expert Ernie Wright performed precise eclipse calculations using data from various NASA sources, while Michala Garrison designed the map, which visually represented the path of totality as a dark band across the United States. Outside this path, purple lines indicated the percentage of the Sun that would be covered by the Moon during the partial eclipse, providing a clear visual guide for observers. To further enhance public understanding, SVS also released an [explanatory video](#) in both English and Spanish, highlighting different areas of the map, describing its features, and detailing what viewers across the country could expect to see during the eclipse. The map and video were made accessible to the public, ensuring widespread educational outreach.

Figure 13

Detailed map of the path and timing of the 2024 eclipse across the US, accounting for the detailed shape of the terrain on both the Earth and the Moon.

The [My NASA Data](#) (MND) project, under the umbrella of the [GLOBE Mission Earth](#) (GME) team, empowers students and teachers worldwide, from 3rd through 12th grade, to analyze and interpret NASA mission data. MND offers a variety of educational materials, including teacher-focused lesson plans, student-facing lessons, interactive tools, and easy access to NASA data through a user-friendly interface. In response to the excitement surrounding the April 8, 2024, total solar eclipse, MND experienced a record-breaking surge in website traffic, attracting 1 million visitors from March 10 to April 10, 2024—a remarkable achievement in just one month. The increase in interest was particularly notable in states along the eclipse's path of totality, with visitors frequently searching for terms like "eclipse," "solar eclipse," and "what is a solar eclipse." Web metrics revealed that the most viewed content included lesson plans and "mini-lessons," with the highest engagement coming from users in Texas, New York, and Illinois.

Among the popular resources were the [MND Featured Mini-Lessons](#) related to the solar eclipse. While some of these resources were specifically designed to prepare audiences for the 2023 and 2024 solar eclipses, most can be used at any time to enhance instruction about the Sun, Earth, and Moon connection. The development of these solar eclipse resources was a collaborative effort between the GLOBE Mission Earth project and NASA HEAT. As shown in the inset, these resources were used across 15 SciAct teams.

The [Cosmic Data Stories](#) (CosmicDS) project created a [Total Solar Eclipse Data Story](#) ([Udomprasert et al., 2024](#)) that allowed users to view what the eclipse

would look like in their sky from any location. [WorldWide Telescope](#) provided the views of the Sun and Moon in the sky based on the requested latitude and longitude. The eclipse path shape file created by SVS (described above) allowed the display of the path of totality across a map of North America within the Data Story. Users could use the map to choose a location and “watch” the eclipse as it would be seen from there, or at a location along the path of totality. Users could also explore historical cloud-cover data from NASA’s Aqua satellite MODIS instrument. An educator and exploration guide made this an easy activity to use in any classroom, and it was used by students from late elementary through early college. The Data Story and Educator Guide were disseminated to their audiences by NASA HEAT, [NASA@My Library](#), and [STEM Enhancement in Earth Science](#) (SEES), as shown in the inset. Before and after April 8, 2024, 24,000 learners from all 50 US states and outside the USA accessed the Total Solar Eclipse Data Story.

Audience Needs-Focused Resource Development

A codesign process for an eclipse curriculum for neurodiverse learners began in 2023, when the NASA’s Neurodiversity Network ([N3](#)) [team](#) wrote a first draft that included extensive use of the NASA [Student Helioviewer](#), which was developed by an earlier SciAct effort ([Connolly et al., 2023](#)), and the creation of a low-cost “sun spotter” for students to use when documenting daily solar activity. The team taught the curriculum to four partner high school teachers, who then worked with their autistic high-school-aged students to engage in the activities over the summer of 2023. An extensive review of their experiences led to additional modifications of the curriculum, which was then posted online

at the [N3 website](#) prior to April 2024. The curriculum was then taught to teachers at three autistic-serving schools along the path of totality (two in Texas and one in Ohio) who worked through the lessons with over

200 students before and after the eclipse in April 2024, with support from four SciAct teams. The highest level of student engagement was observed during hands-on activities ([Nguyen et al., 2024](#)).

The [Exploratorium](#) team created over 40 short [videos](#) (in English and [Spanish](#)) as well as programmatic livestreams of the eclipse. The team worked with [HEAT](#) and [SVS](#) to acquire needed animations and made extensive use of NASA Subject Matter Experts, including scientists from Parker Solar Probe, Moon to Mars Space Weather Analysis Office, Solar Orbiter, [NEBP](#), [GLOBE](#), and [Eclipse Ambassadors](#). Bimonthly meetings with HEAT allowed coordination of resource development to avoid redundancy in content creation. As an example, many teams wanted to create a pinhole projector postcard, but the Polarimeter to UNify the Corona and Heliosphere (PUNCH) mission and ASP were already creating them, and the [NASA PUNCH Outreach Project](#) created a ‘how-to’ video; this allowed the Exploratorium team to focus on other topics. As shown in the inset, Exploratorium materials were used by 10 SciAct teams.

The [Science through Shadows](#) team created three short eclipse videos in both English and Spanish for presentations in both full dome format for planetariums and in rectilinear format for dissemination via [YouTube](#) and related platforms. The first 3-minute video focused on safely viewing the annular eclipse of 2023. The second 5-minute video featured the 2024 total eclipse, along with viewing safety and the solar corona. And the final 4.5-minute film provided context on what causes eclipses. These films were promoted primarily through planetarium and library networks, but were a resource for all of SciAct. Resources were used across 8 SciAct teams.

[NASA@ My Library](#) co-developed bilingual eclipse kits with library staff and patrons in three Texas communities on the path of both eclipses. This partnership focused on local outreach (science, safety, and logistics), development of kits that were replicated for 49 other communities around the nation serving high Spanish speaking populations, and inclusion of activities and resources from other SciAct teams (including [NESEC](#), [Eclipse Soundscapes](#), and others.) These resources were used across 8 SciAct teams.

[Eclipse Soundscapes](#) (ES) focused on engaging people with the eclipse in a multisensory way, making it more accessible ([Perrett et al., 2024](#)). In addition to being available in English and Spanish, ES resources included audio, visual, and text support for learners of all language and science

abilities. Recognizing that time is an inclusion factor, ES split project participation into three different roles, allowing participants to participate in one, two, or all three depending on their needs, interests, time, location, and/or financial constraints. See [Fuller, L., & Severino, M., 2024](#) for a discussion of how this worked in one state. The ES roles for 2024, described below, were Apprentice, Observer, and Data Collector. All three Eclipse Soundscapes roles were created with feedback from Blind and Low Vision (particularly through the National Federation of the Blind), library, educator, and SciAct communities. For each role, inclusion and accessibility were considered, using intentional approaches as summarized in [Figure 14](#).

Figure 14
Graphic summarizing the accessibility and inclusion efforts of the Eclipse Soundscapes project

- The [ES Apprentice role](#) invited participants to learn about eclipses online, for free, and at their own pace. Each lesson was created so that a person could listen, watch, read, use a screen reader, or any combination to ensure accessible eclipse learning. At the end, participants had the opportunity to take a short quiz and earn a certificate. 3,425 people participated as ES apprentices.
- The [ES Observer role](#) was an eclipse day activity that required no equipment and invited people to observe what they heard, felt, and or saw during the eclipse. Making it overtly clear that scientific observations can be gathered using whatever sense is available to an individual was intentional and further shared the message that the “doing” of science can and should be accessible. 3,373 ES Observers submitted their multisensory observations via an accessible survey in 2024.
- The [ES Data Collector role](#) did require equipment: a small audio recording device called an AudioMoth. This device was chosen intentionally because it is open source and the lowest-cost science-grade audio recorder that the ES team was able to find. Approximately 390 accessible kits were given to volunteer data collectors via partnerships with libraries, SciAct partners, the National Federation of the Blind, and a general lottery. The materials needed to participate were also made publicly available for anyone who had the means to create their own kits. The free kits provided by the ES team were made more accessible with the inclusion of braille and tactile “bump dots” on equipment (See [How to Make the AudioMoth More Accessible](#)). Standard equipment directions were rewritten to include references to the bump dots. A total of 1,357 volunteers participated as ES Data Collectors across the annular and total eclipses. 558 of them mailed MicroSD cards of Audiodata they collected, since the internet speed required to upload this data volume would have excluded people from many parts of the US, along with the necessary ancillary information. As of January 2025, the ES team has received complete data sets from 77 annular eclipse sites and 307 total eclipse sites, which are currently being analyzed.

ES was developed iteratively with ongoing feedback from its accessibility partners, formal educators, libraries, volunteers, and participatory science communities. This process began before and continued during and after its beta run for the 2023 annular eclipse, and it remains active as the project enters its post-2024 eclipse data analysis stage. Many of these connections were made possible through SciAct, such as engaging library communities via [NASA @My Library](#), volunteers via [NESEC GLOBE Observer](#) and [Eclipse Ambassadors](#), and receiving feedback from formal educators via [NASA eClips](#). Overall, these resources were used across 15 SciAct teams.

ES, in turn, continuously shared resources and lessons learned, especially on making science more inclusive and accessible, with the greater SciAct community through knowledge-sharing collaborations, internal presentations, and during dedicated collaboration blocks at the SciAct annual in-person meetings. At the 2022 annual SciAct meeting, ES showcased how they made the audio recorder used by ES Data Collectors more accessible by adding tactile bump dots and tactile and complementary online accessible

instructions to guide users to essential ports and switches. This demonstration allowed the SciAct community to see an example of making equipment more accessible and provided ES with valuable feedback on the instructions and wording. Through direct collaborations, ES provided [Learning Ecosystems Northeast](#), [NEBP](#), and [NASA@My Library](#) with accessible ES Data collector kits and training, further expanding their participants' experiences with opportunities and resources to engage even more deeply in eclipse science. [Eclipse Ambassadors](#) leveraged ES resources to reach people in prisons as well as their families ([Scalice et al., 2025](#)). Additionally, ES collaborated with Infiniscope to share a [complementary eclipse curriculum](#) with educators rather than creating it on their own. Even connections to non-eclipse projects proved valuable. Recognizing the shared sense of wonder, [Aurorasaurus](#) and ES collaborated to share information about ES and eclipses with the aurora-watching community. This ongoing interaction with various projects, all aiming to make science more inclusive and accessible, enabled ES to evolve and iterate more effectively. It also provided a platform for other SciAct projects to learn from ES.

ES also greatly benefited from SciAct leadership's awareness of the greater needs of the SciAct community and the combination of teams, infrastructure, and projects that could create the greatest impact. ES utilized eclipse safety training videos and resources from [NASA HEAT](#), and eclipse videos in Spanish from [Science Through the Shadows](#) and NASA [Space Place](#) for the ES Apprentice role. An eclipse Subject Matter Expert (SME) was funded by [SCoPE](#) to connect to underrepresented communities in Uvalde, TX, and National Parks in Texas to facilitate, support, and guide ES Observers and ES Data Collectors for the 2023 annular eclipse and 2024 total solar eclipse. Additionally, an SME was funded by [SCoPE](#) in 2024 to engage Historically Black Colleges and Universities as both ES and [NESEC](#) GLOBE Observer Eclipse participants. NASA's citizen science infrastructure team supported ES and other SciAct teams in developing and sharing resources at NASA eclipse events, such as the NASA-sponsored eclipse viewing event held at the Indianapolis Motor Speedway. [Earth to Sky](#) connected ES, and other SciAct teams, with national parks along the 2024 eclipse path, further expanding the reach of the project and increasing the likelihood of valuable - and coordinated - data collection within natural settings.

6.2. Distributing Resources Through Collaborative Networks

Libraries: Coordinated National Support

Bilingual resources from [NESEC](#), and information about [Eclipse Ambassadors](#) and [Solar System Ambassadors](#) were included with eclipse glasses distributed to 5,200 libraries by [NASA@My Library](#). In addition, registered libraries were able to participate in live and recorded webinars that featured content and resources from over a dozen SciAct teams. The map in [Figure 15](#) below shows the broad reach of these kits and resources. Each spot on the map represents a distribution point. For example, Hawaii has two dots on the map, but those two hubs distributed glasses and resources to approximately 50 other Hawaii libraries.

Figure 15

Eclipse glasses were distributed through libraries located in all 50 states and 4 US territories

[NESEC](#), [GLOBE Mission Earth](#) (GME), and [NASA@My Library](#) also collaborated to recruit, select, and support GLOBE Eclipse Libraries - a group of over 100 U.S. public libraries that committed to offering eclipse programming to engage their communities in GLOBE. By application, a diverse group of more than 100 libraries was selected in terms of geography, communities and audiences served, and types of programming offered (see [Figure 16](#)).

Figure 16

Map showing library locations receiving GLOBE-related eclipse resources across the US

This cross-collaboration leveraged each project’s unique capabilities and resources:

NESEC provided resources to best support library programming, including: bilingual promotional cards, GLOBE Sky Window activity and field guide (English and Spanish), Elementary GLOBE *Do You Know that Clouds Have Names* books (English and Spanish), and air temperature thermometers. NESEC also hosted and recorded seven webinars and four office hours, and an online BaseCamp to foster a community of practice for discussions, planning and programming ideas, FAQ, and on-demand technical support.

NASA@My Library advised on library kit content, promoted the opportunity through the STARnet library network and eclipse programs: e-newsletters, workshops during spring and summer 2023, and two May 2023 informational webinars for over 200 libraries with NESEC, GME, and Eclipse Soundscapes. They also handled the central distribution of the GLOBE Eclipse Library Kits. And, through a competitive application process, selected 52 libraries nationwide in geographic areas with high Latinx populations to receive bilingual (Spanish/English) solar science kits that included GLOBE Eclipse and Eclipse Soundscapes Data Collector resources and equipment (air temperature thermometers and AudioMoths). See Section 7.2, Participatory Science and Collaborative Data Collection, for details.

GME, in collaboration with NESEC, selected a subset of 25 GLOBE Eclipse Libraries to receive infrared thermometers, enabling them to also take surface temperature observations. GME provided GLOBE surface temperature training and ongoing support, and participated in GLOBE Eclipse Library webinars, office hours, and BaseCamp.

For the April 8 solar eclipse, participating libraries offered over 350 programs for more than 32,500 participants. An added benefit for participating library staff is that GLOBE observations of clouds, as well as air and surface temperature, are part of an ongoing program. While there won't be another solar eclipse visible in the United States until 2044, participating library staff now have the training, experience, and interest to continue with GLOBE environmental observations. Evaluation results show 90% of responding library staff are interested in continuing. ([Nyman et al., 2024](#))

Museums: Sharing through a National Network

The [National Informal STEM Education Network](#) (NISE Network) is a community of informal educators and scientists dedicated to supporting learning about STEM across the United States. The NISE Network creates professional learning and public engagement materials on a national level that are designed to be easily adapted by local communities. In preparation for the 2017, 2023, and 2024 solar eclipses, the NISE Network worked with thousands of museum educators nationwide to provide the tools and resources needed to raise their capacity to engage their local communities ([McCarthy & Jackson, 2019](#); [McCarthy et al., 2024a](#)). Professional learning and public engagement efforts included online workshops, conference sessions, training materials, promotional materials, safety guides, event planning guidance, public engagement activities, and evaluation tools.

Efforts focused on increasing the capacity of informal science educators to engage public audiences in their own communities. To avoid duplication of efforts, NISE Network collaborated closely with many institutions and agencies that were developing public engagement resources for the solar eclipse. NISE Network selected high-quality SciAct public engagement resources most relevant and appropriate for informal learning settings and contexts, both inside and outside museums. Collaborative partnerships with SciAct projects included joint presentations at conferences, presenting at NISE Network online workshops, reviewing draft materials, and sharing resources and expertise.

Professional learning resources curated for this effort include:

- **Webpage of resources devised for museum educators:** The NISE Network [solar eclipse-themed web page](#) was designed as a one-stop location for museums and science center educators to find the right resources to engage their local community. Resources were organized by format (such as hands-on activities, presentation slides, posters, imagery, multimedia, videos, citizen science, and event planning). They were categorized in a way that would be most accessible to informal science educators. Many of these resources were from SciAct projects, including the NISE Network itself.
- **Online Workshops:** NISE Network held a series of online workshops prior to each of the solar eclipses covering content such as: the science of eclipses, safe viewing practices, event planning and logistics, live streaming, strategies for adapting programming during cloudy or inclement weather, finding and collaborating with local subject matter experts, citizen science opportunities, community collaborations, and much more.

In total, twenty NISE Network workshops included solar eclipse resources, and six focused entirely on solar eclipse public engagement planning. Over 700 attendees across the United States participated in the six solar eclipse workshops during 2017, 2022, and 2023. Workshop recordings were also publicized through many channels and accessed by thousands of viewers asynchronously. Each workshop was intentionally designed to feature a variety of complementary public engagement resources, including many developed by SciAct projects and infrastructure programs.

- **Professional Conference Outreach:** NISE Network strove to promote awareness of solar eclipse resources through professional meetings and conferences attended by museum, science center, and planetarium professionals. This included concurrent sessions, booths, and events showcasing solar eclipse resources and learning opportunities. Presentations were planned collaboratively with other SciAct projects. See [Table 2](#) for the range of professional audiences reached through the NISE Network and SciAct teams.

Public engagement resources to be used directly with audiences include:

- **Hands-on Activity Kits:** With NASA support, NISE Network developed free physical kits of hands-on materials and professional development resources that were distributed to 350 science and children’s museums across the country, reaching all 50 U.S. states, Washington, DC, Puerto Rico, American Samoa, Guam, and the US Virgin Islands. These kits included resources directly connected to the 2017, 2023, and 2024 solar eclipses. Kit activities complemented and referred to other existing resources developed by other SciAct projects. In addition to the physical kits, activities were available to download at no cost. As with all NISE Network projects, expert input and evaluation played a key role in the development and refinement of all public and professional materials (NISE Network, [2019](#), [2021](#), & [2024](#)). Annual public reach from the 2017 kit of activities was found to be over 1.5 million members of the public during 2017. Public reach for the 2023 kits was over 2 million each. 96% of partners receiving the 2023 Voyage through the Solar System kit reported that they were planning to use the solar eclipse resources ([McCarthy et al., 2024b](#))
- **Digital App to extend learning and provide accessible routes to NASA data on the Sun:** To complement hands-on activities, NISE Network also developed apps to extend family learning at home in both English and Spanish ([DIY Sun Science App](#), [DIY Solar System app](#)). The DIY Sun Science app was designed to make it easy for families and educators to learn about the Sun and includes 15 easy-to-use hands-on activities and a live-data connection. This app allows users to view live images of the Sun from NASA’s Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO) satellite in the Sun Observatory, and see awe-inspiring images and video of the Sun from NASA’s Earth and space observatories. The app was promoted to users of the 2017 and 2023 kits through professional learning resources and opportunities. The apps included resources from SciAct infrastructure, including NASA [Scientific Visualization Studio](#), [Trek](#)s, and input from SciAct subject matter experts.
- **Editable Slide Presentation:** In 2017, the NISE Network distributed “Preparing for a Partial Eclipse: An Event to Remember,” developed by SciAct’s [Night Sky Network](#). In anticipation of the 2023 and 2024 solar

eclipses, NISE Network updated and expanded the editable slideshow with detailed presenter notes to use with staff, volunteers, and public audiences. The slides were designed to be flexible and easily adaptable for specific partner needs and included content and resources from many SciAct projects.

This nationwide public engagement work would not have been possible without the dedicated efforts of many SciAct projects and infrastructure programs working together.

Conferences: Collaboratively Reaching Audiences

A guiding principle for SciAct is to plan collaboratively for conference and event attendance, so as to reach the widest possible audience without unnecessary duplication. [Table 2](#) summarizes many of the venues where SciAct teams shared eclipse content and resources in advance of the eclipses. In most cases, resources from more than one team were shared, even if only one team attended.

Table 2. Conference Collaboration: Comprehensive reach of SciAct program to a wide range of audiences through conferences.

Conference Name	SciAct Teams Attending
American Astronomical Society (AAS)	NASA SCoPE, N3, NEBP, Eclipse Ambassadors, NESEC, Eclipse Soundscapes
American Camp Association	NESEC
American Library Association (ALA) Annual Meeting	NESEC, NASA@ My Library, Eclipse Soundscapes
American Meteorological Society (AMS)	NESEC
American Geophysical Union	NESEC, NASA SCoPE, Infiniscope, N3, Eclipse Ambassadors, NASA@ My Library, Eclipse Soundscapes, GME, Aurorasaurus, HEAT
Association for the Advancement of Participatory Sciences (AAPS)	NASA HEAT, NESEC, Eclipse Soundscapes, Aurorasaurus
Association of Children’s Museums (ACM)	NISE Network
Association of Science Technology Centers (ASTC)	NISE Network, N3, NASA@ My Library
Astronomical League Convention (ALCon)	NISE Network, Eclipse Ambassadors

AwesomeCon	NASA HEAT, NESEC
CENIC	Exploratorium
Geological Society of America (GSA)	NASA SCoPE, Infiniscope
GLOBE Program Annual and Regional Meetings	AREN, GME, NESEC
Great Lake Planetarium Association (GLPA)	NISE Network
International Balloon Fiesta	NESEC
International Planetarium Society	Science through Shadows
Maker STEM Summit	AREN
Michigan Science Teachers Association (MSTA)	AREN
National Association for Interpretation	Earth to Sky, NESEC
National Diversity in STEM (NDiSTEM)	NASA SCoPE
National Science Teaching Association (NSTA)	AREN, GME, Infiniscope, NESEC
Pacific Island Association of Libraries, Museums, and Archives	NASA@ My Library
Science Education Council of Ohio (SECO)	GLOBE Mission Earth
Society for the Advancement of Chicanos/Hispanics and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS)	Eclipse Ambassadors, NASA SCoPE, GLOBE Eclipse
Southeastern Planetarium Association (SEPA)	NISE Network
Space Exploration Educators Conference	NESEC, Eclipse Soundscapes
STEM Learning Ecosystems Community of Practices convenings (SLECoP)	NISE Network
Texas Master Naturalist Program Annual Meeting	NESEC

And Beyond: Ways of Knowing and Circles of Sharing

[Eclipse Ambassadors off the Paths](#) (White et al., 2025) sought to reach underserved audiences in the majority of the country that would experience a partial eclipse. Many cultures have understandings of eclipses that reflect their values and knowledge but differ from the scientific explanation. In the excitement of sharing the science of eclipses, it was important to honor other ways of knowing, not as outdated or in the past tense, but as valuable contributions to our fuller human understanding. A set of cards and slides on [Ways of Knowing: Eclipses Around the World](#) was shared and used widely within SciAct and through related networks (Summer, et al., 2024). It continues to attract attention with cultures from around the world approaching the team to be included.

Many other instances of resource sharing occurred across the SciAct community. [NASA HEAT](#) included [Exploratorium](#) resources in their training modules for NASA personnel, promoted those resources to attendees at ASTC, and distributed their poster on Navajo Knowledge to the public in Albuquerque during the 2023 eclipse. [Exploratorium](#) provided [NISE Network](#) with resources, including videos (Navajo Understanding of eclipses, safe viewing techniques, and building solar views), hands-on activities, and participated in webinars for its museum audience. [NASA@My Library](#) provided links to [Exploratorium](#) livestreams, and Exploratorium teamed with the Citizen Science Eclipse Mega Movie project, through a shared SciAct team member, to provide resources for California's schools at a CENIC conference. Pre-produced videos were also shared with [Earth to Sky](#), and shown in the Mesa Verde Visitor's Center.

7. Examples of Programmatic Collaboration

As part of its HBY participation, [Aurorasaurus](#) (a non-eclipse citizen science project about the aurora) amplified a number of SciAct eclipse-related participatory science projects on multiple occasions. Aurorasaurus also collaborated with HBY to create a plain language Heliophysics ["zine" activity](#) that was used for outreach and education about the eclipse.

7.1. Inclusive In-Person Engagement

For the week leading up to the total solar eclipse, the [Earth to Sky Partnership](#) (ETS), [NASA Earth Science Division](#), [NESEC](#), [NOAA Space Weather Office](#) (SWO), [Smoky Mountains STEM Collaborative](#) (SMSC), [Eclipse Soundscapes](#), and [Eclipse Ambassadors Off the Path](#) joined the National Park Service (NPS) for eclipse engagement in [Hot Springs National Park](#) in Hot Springs, AR. This effort was intended to engage in as many school and community events as possible. Over the week, the team made nearly 20,000 contacts with community members and visitors to the area.

The team chose to plan one component in particular - the Eclipse Festival - with inclusivity in mind. For the festival, solar film canopies (See [Figure 17](#)) were created, allowing those who use wheelchairs or have difficulty putting on solar viewers to view the eclipse with ease while protecting their vision. The canopies were wildly popular with everyone who attended the event. One lesson learned was to make sure the height of the canopy was tall enough that most people could not touch the film while standing underneath. It also would have been better to have a sign explaining why they were onsite, to create awareness of its intended purpose, to make others aware, and to ensure access for those it was designed for.

In the two festival days prior to the eclipse, the Eclipse Soundscapes team greeted festival attendees at a table and shared information about how to experience the eclipse in a multisensory way, and invited everyone to participate in NASA volunteer science as ES Observers. Before sharing multi-sensory eclipse experience information at the festival, the Eclipse Soundscapes team met with members of the Hot Springs National Park Service to deploy AudioMoths at five different remote areas of Hot Springs National Park to collect audio data (See [Figure 18](#)). In several of those same locations, the Hot Springs National Park team is also collecting their own audio recordings using a different style audio recorder. The ES team hopes this will lead to data sharing and collaboration with the NPS.

Figure 17
Solar film canopy set-up and people using it to view the eclipse (inset).

Figure 18

National Park Service Partners deploy an AudioMoth at Hot Springs National Park.

The team also deployed three [LightSound](#) devices with an external speaker at three eclipse viewing locations: West Mountain, Hot Springs Mountain, and Arlington Lawn. Harvard University created this sonification tool for those with visual impairments for the 2017 eclipse. The devices were activated 15 minutes before the eclipse and ran throughout all phases of the eclipse. It was powerful to hear the device and feel the shift in temperature as the device changed in output pitch from high to low and then back to high. The devices were at all tabling events so attendees would know they would be present, and active, and understand what purpose they served. A sign was placed at each table explaining how the device worked and why it was there. On the day of the eclipse, it would have been helpful to have a larger sign explaining the device and have the device out of reach so that the sonification pattern was not interrupted by visitors during the eclipse. A power supply was also essential.

At one table at each site, a set of tactile plates explained what was happening during the eclipse in Braille. The plates showed the alignment in space of the Sun, Moon, and Earth during an eclipse, solar features (e.g., prominences, flares, loops, sunspots), layers of the Sun from core to corona, and a recreation of an 1800s drawing of a total solar eclipse in thermoform created by the PUNCH mission outreach team. One team member was responsible for speaking to these tactile plates during the festival.

Each site had concrete walls for people to rest on, and all were encouraged to set up chairs, blankets, or any other comforts at the viewing sites. Access to the mountain sites was by shuttle only to avoid vehicle movement within the viewing sites. The team also covered cultural sensitivities that may be encountered during eclipse engagement and was trained on how to be sensitive to potential community needs and how to respond if a concern was expressed.

An area along Arlington Lawn was set up with a low sensory tent. This area provided relief to families with neurodivergent children and an opportunity to take a break from the crowds as needed. The tent was fully enclosed and away from the main area.

Official sites within the national park were monitored and staffed by teams consisting of at least one subject matter expert and volunteers to communicate safe viewing protocols and explain the stages of the eclipse as

totality approached. A loudspeaker was used at the three main sites to allow one member of the team to describe what was happening during the eclipse phases and to relay safety protocol. With several larger prominences visible during totality, it provided those gathered with details of what they were witnessing.

7.2. Participatory Science and Collaborative Data Collection

SciAct enables the exchange of information between projects, thereby enhancing awareness of projects' goals and methodologies, and fosters cross-collaborations to leverage assets and expertise across teams. A powerful example is intentional and collaborative data collection across two participatory science projects - [Eclipse Soundscapes](#) (ES; described above under “Sharing Accessibility & Inclusion Expertise section) and [NESEC](#) (whose [GLOBE Observer](#) citizen science project engages volunteers to collect air temperature measurements and observations of sky conditions using the GLOBE Eclipse module in the GLOBE Observer mobile app) – that was amplified through cross-collaborations with NASA [SCoPE](#) and [NASA@ My Library](#).

Through their collaboration, ES and NESEC encouraged participants in the GLOBE Eclipse project to also engage with Eclipse Soundscapes and vice versa. To this end, they partnered with NASA@ My Library to include ES audio recording equipment (AudioMoths) and GLOBE air temperature thermometers in their bilingual (English and Spanish) solar science library kits distributed to 49 libraries serving communities with large Hispanic populations. This effort aimed to increase public participation in scientific exploration and collect co-located temperature, cloud, and environmental audio data, enriching volunteers' scientific engagement and increasing the value of the data they collected. This shared dataset, collected from locations across the nation (see [Figure 19](#)), could significantly enhance understanding of the eclipse's effects on the environment and wildlife.

SciAct intentionally sets aside time for projects to meet and work on collaborations during its annual in-person meeting. During this time, ES and NESEC mapped out and then later expanded upon and implemented these collaborative efforts, which included:

- Co-presenting webinars and question and answer sessions, including [GO Connect Observing Eclipses](#), [Two for One: GLOBE Eclipse and Eclipse Soundscapes](#) (links to YouTube videos).
- Cross-promotion: e.g., co-creating slides and handouts to be shared during events, cross-linking and posting information on respective project websites (e.g., [blog on experiencing an eclipse with all your senses](#)).
- Sharing best practices and resources, e.g., [Planning and Timeline](#) webinar and [program planning template](#) for the April 8 Eclipse, and [notes from the joint Q&A session](#).

Additionally, ES and NESEC both collaborated with the same NASA SCoPE-funded subject matter expert, [Dr. Valerie Johnson](#), who engaged six HBCUs along the 2024 eclipse path in both ES and GLOBE Eclipse projects. The teams provided Dr. Johnson and her recruited volunteers with equipment and training. Together, they co-planned and promoted complementary training and eclipse science activities to ensure active

participation from HBCUs in eclipse observation and data collection, thereby enriching the educational experiences of volunteers and creating more opportunities for co-located data collection.

Figure 19

Locations during the April 8 solar eclipse where observations were submitted for GLOBE Eclipse (blue dots) or ES Audio Data Collectors (red dots). Credit: Andrew Clark, IGES, using data from ES and GLOBE.

The partnership between these four projects under the SciAct program exemplifies the power of collaborative data collection and public engagement in scientific exploration. By leveraging participatory science and intentionally fostering collaboration, these initiatives will enrich the scientific understanding of solar eclipses' effects on the environment and wildlife. The combined efforts in data collection, community engagement, and educational outreach have created a comprehensive dataset that enhances the value and impact of the research. The involvement of SCoPE, particularly in engaging historically marginalized communities and HBCUs, and NASA@ My Library, by creating bilingual materials in English and Spanish, further underscores the commitment to inclusive and diverse scientific participation. These multifaceted collaborations not only advance scientific knowledge but also inspire and educate a more diverse cross-section of the public, showcasing the transformative potential of collaborative scientific endeavors.

A related collaboration among NESEC, GME, and the US GLOBE office planned and conducted a series of virtual workshops to train a cohort of educators to use GLOBE in the context of the eclipse ([Giarratano et al., 2024](#)). Evaluation of these workshops demonstrated gains in teachers' confidence in doing and teaching earth science research.

The [Nationwide Eclipse Ballooning Project](#) ([Saad et al., 2024](#)) involved 850+ student participants on 53 teams, primarily at the college level, in conducting innovative stratospheric ballooning campaigns during the 2023 annular and 2024 total solar eclipses. The campaigns' science goals were ambitious: to examine the atmospheric response to the cold, dark shadow of the eclipse and to capture the stunning view from a space-like perspective. The teams' participants successfully produced significant science results ([Shetye et al., 2025](#); [Vesa et al., 2025](#)), and more importantly, gained valuable learning in the process. For example, NEBP evaluation ([Covitt, et al., 2024](#)) revealed that while prior to the eclipses, 63% of the participants felt no to moderate overlap between themselves and STEM professionals; after the eclipses, 69% felt large to almost complete overlap. NEBP benefited from cross-collaborations with other SciAct teams, including Eclipse Soundscapes and [Science through Shadows](#). Each NEBP team received an Audiomoth and was encouraged to participate in Soundscapes. During the annular eclipse, the Science through Shadows team captured interviews and video footage of eclipse participatory science efforts associated with two NEBP teams. This will be combined with footage from three Citizen CATE 2024 teams in Texas and Arkansas to support the production of a Science through Shadows episode on eclipse participatory science to be released in Summer 2025. All told, the NEBP experience was hugely impactful and continues to benefit participants through data analysis and knowledge-sharing efforts.

7.3 Professional Learning and Resources for Near-Path Learners

The [AEROKATS and ROVER Education Network](#) (AREN) focuses on supporting K-12 educators and citizen scientists with kite- and surface-based remote sensing. Due to AREN's home base location in Wayne, Michigan, a unique opportunity arose to reach a large population in Wayne County - including Detroit - where a 99% eclipse would occur. While locations in totality might have been planning for years, Wayne County had many educational organizations that were not aware of the upcoming April eclipse in time to make adequate preparations for safe observing.

In November 2023, AREN began making plans to support the educational community and ensure the safety of environmental observations related to the eclipse. They created professional learning materials focusing on safety, basic eclipse information, and ideas for hands-on learning activities using resources from AREN and a number of other SciAct partners. These were presented at in-person professional learning sessions, including the Wayne RESA Maker STEM Summit, Michigan Science Teachers Association, and Wayne County Science Leaders Network. A virtual learning session was conducted for Detroit Public Schools Community District (DPSCD) with about 150 educators in attendance. AREN was able to supply over 70,000 eclipse glasses to

participants, with 50,000 sets specifically going to students and educators in DPSCD. Digital resources were provided to all school administrators and educators who expressed interest in receiving solar eclipse glasses.

The AREN team received overwhelmingly positive responses from participants expressing appreciation for the eclipse resources that were provided. “What a wonderful day of learning we had all across the district - from big kids to little ones, from administrators to central office employees, everyone was able to get out and enjoy science. It just doesn't get any better than building community through science. AREN's partnership made this a reality, and we are so grateful for the investment in our students.”

7.4 Connecting and Supporting Subject Matter Experts

[NASA SMD Community of Practice for Education](#) (SCoPE) aims to connect NASA science content experts with SciAct teams - in this case, to enhance public understanding of eclipses. Over an eight-month period, SCoPE engaged over 25 experts from across the United States to facilitate eclipse-related knowledge dissemination among learners of all ages. These efforts were strategically aligned with SciAct events, either hosted or facilitated at locations along the paths of annularity or totality, and incorporating a blend of virtual and in-person educational formats. These events not only disseminated information centered around the eclipse but also highlighted the diverse cultural and personal connections of these experts with science, thereby enriching the educational experience.

To enhance the efficacy of the knowledge-sharing initiatives, eclipse training and resources were provided to these content experts. Training utilized materials from [NASA HEAT](#) and leveraged the digital platform of [Infinscope](#) to deliver this on-their-own training. Additionally, a broad array of resources organized by audience age groups was compiled from across NASA and the SciAct community to equip these experts with relevant and engaging materials to support their event. For example, a presentation deck from [NASA@MyLibrary](#) and educational activities from NASA HEAT were organized and made accessible. These resources were curated to ensure that experts were well-prepared to engage and educate audiences in a variety of settings, whether virtual or in-person, enhancing their capability to communicate complex scientific concepts effectively.

7.5 Meeting the Needs of Specific Communities

[Native Earth | Native Sky](#) (NENS) held several teacher professional development workshops on the eclipse. The first was a large workshop in February 2024 for 110 teachers from across Oklahoma, held at Oklahoma State University. Teachers heard eclipse science from a NASA Subject Matter Expert (coordinated by the [SCoPE](#) team) and received classroom resources about eclipses, including videos, weblinks, and a PowerPoint presentation to use with students. They also received training on the NENS lesson “[The Story of Tvshka and Walo](#).” This lesson, which meets both Oklahoma and Next Generation Science Standards (NGSS) for eighth grade, was co-created with the Choctaw Nation of Oklahoma and includes a traditional Choctaw story about two young boys who travel far from the traditional Choctaw homelands to meet the Sun. The teachers heard Native American perspectives about the solar eclipse and learned when and how to use Native eclipse stories in

their classrooms. All participants received classroom sets of eclipse glasses, as well as educator resources from NASA SciAct teams and a copy of a book on solar eclipses. One teacher said, “The Native perspective was particularly enlightening. And receiving two books and a class set of glasses is incredible!” Another teacher commented, “Practicing the models of the eclipse really helped solidify my understanding.”

NENS also did professional development workshops at all six elementary school sites in Stillwater, OK, between March and early April 2024 to reach ~175 teachers. At one elementary school, the NENS team taught a group of ~75 fifth-grade students, who then were responsible for teaching their younger peers about eclipse science. The Stillwater teachers also received classroom sets of eclipse glasses. One Stillwater teacher shared: “This isn’t as scary as I thought it would be! I was worried to take my students outside before.” Finally, NENS distributed eclipse glasses to neighboring Native American Nations throughout Oklahoma. A total of 22,000 eclipse glasses were provided to Oklahoma teachers through NENS training offerings.

8. Examples of Knowledge Sharing

The [Exploratorium](#) team had worked on eight prior eclipses and generously shared learnings from this experience with SciAct. The Exploratorium provided [NASA HEAT](#) with its independent evaluation reports from 2017 to share its lessons learned and suggestions for future projects. Through *Community of Practice* meetings organized by SciAct, information was shared on how to scout for locations within the path of totality generally, and specifically on scouting trips that had already occurred for the 2023 and 2024 eclipses. For example, photographs and contact information were provided for possible locations in Texas, including Kerrville and Fredericksberg; and location support was provided for the [NEBP](#). These meetings also were important to coordinate the use of SMEs across the various projects. SMD’s digital manager also held meetings to help coordinate and support the projects’ telescope technicians. The Exploratorium was able to provide valuable information around telescope alignments, filters, and false color adjustments to ensure that live streams would provide similar images to avoid public confusion. HEAT was also able to serve as a second, confirming source for front-page articles in the NY Times about Navajo eclipse knowledge and the Exploratorium’s history of broadcasting eclipses.

The NESEC team trained Science Activation partners, including ten SciAct projects, and an HBCU network funded under NASA SCoPE. Additional external partners that received training included libraries, Texas Master Naturalists, and Civil Air Patrol; the latter was a major contributor of observations during the eclipse. To support partners, NESEC and GLOBE Mission Earth provided a blog about how to involve students in data collection. Most training events and online materials encouraged partners to also collect data for NASA Eclipse Soundscapes to provide co-located observations of temperature changes and animal behavior.

8.1. Implementing Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

Both Infiniscope and ES aimed to address the need for comprehensive and accessible solar eclipse curricula that cater to a diverse student population, including English Learners (ELs), bilingual English/Spanish learners,

and students at different learning levels. Recognizing that existing science resources predominantly target grade-level-ready, English-speaking students, the collaborative effort between Infiniscope and ES developed differentiated lessons using a UDL approach to better serve all learners. UDL results in flexible lessons and materials that can be customized and modified for individual needs, focusing on using a variety of ways to engage in learning. This approach allowed the teams to create resources that support a wide range of learners, including those with diverse linguistic backgrounds and varying levels of prior knowledge. The curriculum's emphasis on UDL ensured that every student could access and benefit from the educational materials, fostering a more inclusive and effective learning environment. The goal was to work together to prepare students for the April 8, 2024, total solar eclipse and to provide teachers with ready-to-use, NGSS-aligned curricula that minimize preparation time.

- The [ES curriculum](#) featured three NGSS-aligned and detailed lesson plans designed for upper middle school students: "What and When is Solar Eclipse Maximum?," "Nature During a Solar Eclipse," and "Multi-sensory Observing." Each lesson followed a structured format that included introductory activities ("Do Now"), readings, videos, and graphic organizers, employing the Gradual Release of Responsibility (GRR) method ([Pearson & Gallagher, 1983](#)) to support student learning. They also include formative assessment options and modified materials for students of various learning and linguistic levels. Additional activities, such as the "Eclipse Day Observation Activity" and the "Post Eclipse Day - Data Literacy Classroom Activity," were created for both classroom and at-home use, encouraging students to engage in scientific exploration during the 2024 total solar eclipse by recording multisensory observations. The curriculum was praised by teachers from the 2024 ES cohort for its ready-to-use resources and its effectiveness in engaging students and accommodating diverse learning needs.
- Infiniscope's curriculum, "[Kingdom in Peril](#)," is a web-based series of lessons designed and aligned with the NGSS. This curriculum leverages [NASA's Eyes on the Solar System](#), a 3D visualization application, to allow learners to explore the three key factors contributing to the total eclipse phenomenon: arrangement, inclination, and shadow size. Each lesson provides automatic, personalized feedback to each student and is accompanied with comprehensive educational support, including downloadable NGSS alignment documents to assist teachers in classroom implementation. The curriculum follows the 5-E inquiry model ([Bybee et al., 2006](#)), incorporating narrative descriptions, recording sheets for students, and rubrics for both formative and summative assessments. This structure ensures that teachers have the necessary tools to facilitate engaging and effective science instruction. The series is offered in both [English](#) and [Spanish](#), with a focus on grades 5–8.

Once the curricula were available, this partnership extended support to 189 educators from states within the [April 2024 total solar eclipse's path](#) (map), spanning from Arkansas to New York. The educators were granted stipends, equipped with curriculum training, and furnished with solar-viewing glasses for their students. Leading up to the eclipse, students in the selected schools learned about eclipses using the Infiniscope curriculum and, using the ES curriculum, broadened their scientific observation beyond the visual to better

understand how eclipses affect nature. Come eclipse day, each student received NASA-provided solar viewers to safely witness the event. Following the [ES Observer Role](#) protocols, they recorded observations using whichever senses were available to them, not just sight. These data were then shared with NASA as part of their volunteer science data collection efforts. The ES Education Director notes that, “Integrating informal participatory science ... opportunities, like the ES project, into formal education provides students with opportunities to implement what they've learned in the classroom in a real-world, hands-on setting and contribute to real NASA science in the process.”

This partnership exemplifies how intentional collaboration within learning communities like SciAct can have transformative impacts in the communities they serve. Surveys revealed that educators found these lessons well-organized and effective in supporting various learning levels, emphasizing the importance of real-world phenomena in enhancing scientific understanding. One teacher shared, “My students are thrilled to be part of this opportunity and contribute to a NASA study. The chance to collect real data as citizen scientists has literally made them sit up straighter with excitement!” Another teacher said, “I am truly honored to be part of this program and share this experience with my students. They are more engaged and excited than I’ve seen them with any other unit of study this year.” Students were especially excited about collecting real data during the eclipse to contribute to NASA science, with one teacher stating, “It has been awesome to see my students so excited and intrigued about the eclipse!” In a new alternative middle school focused on real-world experiences, a teacher emphasized, “This is a great opportunity for our kids to see science in real-time and be part of it. I am very excited to take all of our students outside on Monday to observe the world around us.” The team’s comprehensive evaluation strategy and results, as well as additional details on the collaboration and curricula, can be found in [Swann et al., 2025](#).

By combining their expertise and resources, Infiniscope and ES have enriched educational experiences, providing students with high-quality, real-world materials that ignite scientific curiosity. The initiative's focus on inclusivity, through differentiated and multi-sensory learning experiences, ensures that all learners, regardless of background or ability, can access and benefit from the curriculum. As students and teachers prepared for the April 8, 2024, total solar eclipse, this project highlights the critical role of collaboration in delivering comprehensive and engaging educational content, setting a standard for future endeavors in science education.

8.2. Enacting Inclusive Engagement Methods

[Eclipse Ambassadors](#) connected with the Marshal Project’s *News Inside*, offering to send the [Eclipse Soundscapes](#) (ES) citizen science project to incarcerated learners. More than 70 inmates from 54 institutions participated in recording and returning data. The Eclipse Ambassador team modified the online data entry to a two-sided paper sheet, allowing incarcerated participants to record their observations manually. These observations were then mailed back to the Eclipse Ambassador team for digitization and returned to the ES

team. Certificates of participation were mailed to both the inmates and their parole officers to ensure a record of their involvement in the program.

Eclipse Soundscapes (ES) connected with Dr. Brent Pease of [Sounds of Nature | PEASE Lab](#), who learned of the project from a colleague. Dr. Pease runs a citizen science project, Sounds of Nature, that partners with the public in and around Illinois to deploy AudioMoth sound recorders on private property. Through collaboration with ES, nearly 100 Sounds of Nature volunteers, who already owned AudioMoth devices, participated as ES Data Collectors, resulting in audio data submission from 78 additional sites.

Eclipse Soundscapes connected with [SciStarter](#) and became a [SciStarter Affiliate](#) project ([Severino et al., 2025](#)). “SciStarter is a globally acclaimed, online citizen science hub where thousands of projects, searchable by location, topic, age level, etc., have been registered by individual project leaders or imported through partnerships with federal governments, NGOs, and universities.” Being an affiliate project meant that participation in any of the Eclipse Soundscapes roles completed before April 15, 2024 could be credited to a participant’s SciStarter Dashboard. This collaboration led to the participation of 191 ES Apprentices, 162 ES Observers, and 105 ES Data Collectors. NESEC has partnered with SciStarter since 2018. From August 1, 2023 to April 30, 2024, there were 585 SciStarter users who added GLOBE Observer Clouds to their dashboard.

9. After the Eclipses: Extending the Impact

While the eclipses of 2023-24 are now behind us, the SciAct community is still going strong. The collaborations established for the eclipse have further strengthened relationships within the community and will continue to bear fruit for a long time. Out of the eclipse engagement, new partnerships were also forged. The [Eclipse Ambassador](#) and [HEAT](#) teams are currently collaborating on an update to the [Night Sky Network](#) Magnetic Sun resources for informal educators. Those will be released online and distributed to SciAct networks in 2025, to allow them to further build on audiences’ engagement with the eclipse, aurora, and all things Sun.

The Heliophysics Big Year continued through Parker Solar Probe’s closest approach to the Sun in December 2024. An extensive auroral outbreak in May 2024 and again in August and October 2024 further ramped up public interest in our planet’s relationship with the Sun. The [Aurorasaurus](#) project received a record number of volunteer reports during the May event, and continues to gather reports of the large aurora displays at outreach-oriented Report-A-Thons. SciAct projects were able to activate and share applicable resources from this expert partner quickly. In January 2025, the Eclipse Ambassadors [Winter Field School](#) in Fairbanks, Alaska, introduced students to space physics graduate studies in topics such as electromagnetism, observations of aurora, data reduction, and instrumentation. The program was held in collaboration with Aurorasaurus and the Heliophysics Big Year, and included further collaborations with GLOBE and other projects. [NASA](#)

[HEAT](#) launched a [Math webinar series](#) in November 2023, which continued through December 2024. Topics included solar maximum and the Parker Solar Probe’s record-breaking trajectory.

In collaboration with SMEs and outreach leadership with both Parker Solar Probe and the PUNCH mission, Episodes 5-7 of [Science through Shadows](#) feature NASA’s efforts to study the heliosphere using a range of techniques. Released in Fall 2024 to close out the Helio Big Year, [Episode 5: Humanity Touches the Sun](#) features an in situ study of the Sun by the Parker Solar Probe. [Episode 6: The Sun Touches Humanity](#) was released prior to launch of the NASA PUNCH mission, which will provide continuous monitoring of the inner heliosphere from 6 solar radii out to 1AU using four Earth-orbiting wide field imagers. And [Episode 7: Doing NASA Eclipse Science](#) will feature participatory science efforts associated with both of the US eclipses this decade, including efforts by the [NEBP](#), [Citizen CATE 2024](#), [Eclipse Soundscapes](#), and [Eclipse Megamovie 2024](#). The focus of this episode on participatory science follows [Episode 4: Chasing Polymele’s Shadow](#), which also features volunteers contributing to NASA science through stellar occultations, which are similar to eclipses but involve asteroids in our Solar System passing in front of distant stars.

Teams involved in participatory science for the eclipse shared their science results in several fora, including the Fall 2024 American Geophysical Union conference, which included a Union session co-convened by SciAct team members. Several science papers are also planned. In addition, all of the data recorded by the Nationwide Eclipse Ballooning Project (NEBP) is in the process of being uploaded to Dryad, a data-publishing platform, making it accessible to scientists worldwide and to the public. This includes atmospheric science data as well as engineering data recorded on hundreds of balloon flights before, during, and after totality during both the annular and the total solar eclipse. Dozens of NEBP ballooning teams, located at colleges and universities across the country, are also continuing to develop their expertise and train new students by focusing now on atmospheric dynamics above the Gulf Stream and radiation dynamics in the stratosphere due to the current solar maximum cycle.

Many of the resources developed by SciAct projects can be readily adapted and reused for future eclipses. For example, the CosmicDS team made only minor modifications to the Solar Eclipse 2024 Data Story to create a new [Solar Eclipse 2026 Data Story](#), using a new eclipse path shape file also provided by SVS. The Exploratorium team is already planning work around the 2026-2028 eclipses, with consultation from other SciAct teams.

Returning to the SciAct vision shared in Section 1, the solar eclipses served as a crucible to strengthen and deepen collaborations between SciAct teams. New ways to actively involve learners in advancing human knowledge were pioneered and evaluated and will influence ongoing SciAct activities.

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Appendix A: Survey Items and Alignment to Research Questions

Survey Item	Question(s)
1. Which SciAct Project Team is this report for?	Identify reporting team
2. (checkbox) Which of the following Infrastructure teams had assets that you utilized in your eclipse efforts? (Select all that apply)	Question 1: To what extent did NASA Infrastructure teams provide eclipse assets and resources to teams?

<p>3. (checkbox grid) Make a selection where you collaborated with another SciAct team (rows) in any of the following ways (columns) for the 2024 Solar Eclipse:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Product/Resource Sharing = your team utilized an asset or resource (video, presentation, handouts, etc) from this team. This is <i>one-directional</i> about USAGE, only select this if you used their resources, NOT if you gave resources out to them. Programmatic Collaboration = you collaborated to design or deliver a program, like a webinar or a workshop, together (you can both have a check for each other). Knowledge Sharing = you had dedicated and substantial guidance from the team in the design of your own eclipse efforts (you can both have a check for each other). Other = if the nature of your collaboration is not represented in these categories, then select this and add details in the space following. 	<p>Questions 2 & 3:</p> <p>Data from this question would inform both the nature, and volume, of collaboration among funded teams within the network. High density clusters of teams would identify potential collaboration success stories.</p>
<p>Please add details if you selected "Other" in the previous two questions.</p>	<p>Enables details to be added to Question 2.</p>
<p>Is there anything else that you would like to share about your cross-collaborations within SciAct around the 2024 Solar Eclipse?</p>	<p>Capture outliers or additional insights into collaborations across NASA that were external to SciAct.</p>

Appendix B: Team names and Corresponding Abbreviations used in Figures 6-8

Aerokats and Rovers Education Network	AREN
American Camp Association	ACA
AMNH OpenSpace	OpenSpace
Arctic and Earth SIGNS	Arctic and Earth SIGNS
NASA ASTRO CAMP	NASA ASTRO CAMP
Astronomy Activation Ambassadors	AAA

Astronomy Picture of the Day	APOD
Aurorasaurus	Aurorasaurus
Cosmic Storytelling with NASA Data	CosmicDS
Earth to Sky	Earth to Sky
Eclipse Ambassadors	EA
Eclipse Soundscapes: Citizen Science	ES:CSP
Engaging Hispanic Communities	EHC
GLOBE Mission Earth	GME
Idaho Dark Sky STEM Network	Idaho DSSN
Infiniscope	Infiniscope
Learning Ecosystems Northeast (GMRI)	LENE
Museum & Informal Education Alliance	M&IEA
NASA @ My Library	NASA @ My Library
NASA Earth Science Education Collaborative	NESEC
NASA eClips	eClips
NASA Heliophysics Education Action Team	HEAT
NASA SMD Community of Practice for Education	SCoPE
NASA's Neurodiversity Network (N3)	N3
NASA's Universe of Learning	NASA's UoL
National Informal STEM Education Network	NISENet
Nationwide Eclipse Ballooning	NEBP
Native Earth Native Sky	Native Earth Native Sky

Navigating the Path of Totality	Exploratorium
Night Sky Network	NSN
PLACES	PLACES
Planetary Resources and Content Heroes	ReaCH
Science through Shadows	StS
Scientific Visualization Studio	SVS
Smoky Mountains STEM Collaborative	SMSC
Solar System Ambassadors	SSA
STEM Ecosystems to Broaden Participation in Authentic STEM Learning	STEM Ecosystems
STEM Enhancement in Earth Science	SEES

Footnotes

1. SciAct tallies learner interactions rather than unique learners because we don't track individuals across teams, or even across multiple offerings from the same team. [↵](#)
2. The total solar eclipse was visible along a narrow track stretching from Texas to Maine on April 8, 2024. A partial eclipse was visible throughout all 48 contiguous U.S. states and into southeast Alaska. [↵](#)

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